

**THE POSITION AND ROLE OF WOMEN AND CHILDREN IN CONFLICT HOTSPOTS WITH
REFERENCES TO WOMEN'S ACTIVITIES, POLITICIANS AND OTHER PROFESSIONALS IN
THE MANAGEMENT AND RESOLUTION OF CONFLICT**

FLORENCE IROAGALACHI

Development Specialist, Central Bank of Nigeria.

Corresponding Author: firoagalachi@yahoo.com

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Abstract

Conflicts have devastating consequences on women and children, exposing them to gender-based violence, forced displacement, economic deprivation, and loss of access to essential services. This paper examines the position and role of women and children in conflict hotspots, focusing on Nigeria, where insurgency, communal violence, and terrorism have led to widespread instability. Using Feminist Theory and Human Security Theory, the paper explores how systemic inequalities and security threats intensify the vulnerabilities of women and children during conflicts while also highlighting their active participation in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Key findings reveal that women and children suffer disproportionately from sexual violence, forced labour, human trafficking, and disruptions in education and healthcare, particularly in conflict zones such as the North-East (Boko Haram insurgency), the Middle Belt (herder-farmer clashes), and the Niger Delta (militancy and resource conflicts). However, despite these adversities, women play significant roles in mediation, advocacy, community rehabilitation, and post-conflict economic recovery. The paper underscores the need for stronger legal frameworks, increased female representation in peace negotiations, economic empowerment initiatives, and improved access to education and psychosocial support for survivors of conflict-related trauma. By addressing these issues through gender-sensitive policies and community-driven peace efforts, Nigeria can achieve more sustainable post-conflict reconstruction and long-term stability.

Keywords: Conflict, Gender-Based Violence, Forced Displacement, Peacebuilding, Women's Empowerment, Children in Conflict, Post-Conflict Reconstruction

Introduction

The channel through which every life is given is a woman, this goes to show the essential role the female gender plays in human existence. The most crucial roles played by women include being mothers, destiny moulders, and wives in societies. They are tasked with the function of birthing lives and nurturing. In most African states, women are limited to domestic activities while men are reserved for major work otherwise called hard labour (Dimandja, 2020; Aghaei et al, 2022). It is imperative to state that conflicts have made an extreme impact on human history usually resulting in diverse consequences for members of societies and individuals. In current-day conflict zones, mainly in areas such as the global South, when conflicts occur, especially during armed conflicts, children and women most times are victimized or are negatively impacted. Women are vulnerable to gender-based violence when conflicts occur, such as rape, torture, discrimination, and other violence. (Shea & Christian, 2016; Noor & Binte-Saleem, 2017).

The impact of women and children in conflict has been greatly documented on a global level. The United Nations (UN) defines a conflict hotspot as a region where conflict and violence have a disproportionate impact on civilians, especially women and children (UNICEF, 2019). From the genocides in Rwanda and Bosnia to the conflicts in Syria, Yemen, and Afghanistan, the consequences of the conflicts on these vulnerable individuals are undeniable. Syria has been emerged in a brutal civil war since 2011 with a large number of people displaced and thousands killed, this situation had a major impact on women and children, especially with the existing gender inequality and exposing them to specific vulnerabilities. Women within this region faced extreme levels of sexual and gender-based violence (SGBV) due to the ongoing conflict at that time, cases of rape, forced marriages, and others were widely dominant, especially in such areas. The children in this region were affected in ways of education disruption with over 2.1 million children being out of school as of 2020 (UNICEF, 2020). In conflict hotspots, women and children often bear the brunt of instability, yet women's roles as activists, politicians, and professionals in peacebuilding and conflict resolution are increasingly recognized as critical to sustainable solutions, a perspective that aligns with broader analyses of societal dynamics, such as the exploration of civilizational interests by Ibe, Iroye, & Ibeunjo (2024), who highlight the importance of inclusive approaches in addressing complex challenges within unstable regions.

The Democratic Republic of the Congo has faced a similar fate as in this region, women and children have been affected by issues of rape, forced labour, and trafficking and are targets for abduction which emanates from conflict. The children are often recruited by armed forces and sometimes as sex slaves. Afghanistan on the other hand, has been affected by conflict for over a long time and just like other regions, women and children are victimized or subjected to major displacements. These are just a few countries where their women and children have been affected majorly by conflict. Women and children often suffer from gender-based violence, displacement, forced labour, sexual violence, extreme human rights abuses, and abduction (UNICEF, 2020). In addition, they frequently face the erosion of social structures that once provided protection and security. Children in conflict zones are most at times seen as vulnerable victims, facing recruitment by armed groups either forcefully or voluntarily, exposed to violence amongst others. Beyond the direct engagement in conflicts, children also encounter the loss of their families, education, and stable living conditions, and their futures are severely affected. Women and children go through psychological and physical trauma and most times not all of them can recover leading to the death of many (Alhyari et al., 2020).

Africa is home to multiple continual and past conflicts that have had tremendous consequences for women and children. Armed conflicts, including civil wars, insurgencies, ethnic violence, and terrorism have created a humanitarian crisis for a vulnerable population. African countries have been at the center of major conflicts and brutalization in most parts of the world. Women and Children of these regions have been victimized encountering cases of gender-based violence, exploitation especially due to a lack of awareness of their rights yet they still bear the responsibility of caring for their families, managing households, and resolving domestic conflicts in their communities (Razi et al., 2019). Women in one way or another have contributed to ensuring peace in society but they are still considered vulnerable and mostly limited by society. According to UN Women (2020), one of the major impacts of conflict on women and children of Africa is sexual and gender-based violence, women and little girls are subjected to systematic sexual slavery, rape forced marriages, and other forms of violence sexually. The United Nations has repeatedly highlighted the use of sexual violence as a weapon of war in several African conflicts. In

the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), for example, armed groups have employed rape as a tactic to instill fear in communities and break down social cohesion (UN Women, 2020).

In furtherance, another core problem associated with conflict is that it led to mass displacement, with millions of people fleeing their homes and communities. This disruption of social and economic structures forces women and children to live in refugee camps or urban areas, often in poverty and without basic services (Njoku, 2017). The economic impact of conflict is often felt hardest by women and children, who lose livelihoods, assets, and access to resources. Women, especially those who become heads of households, bear the burden of maintaining their families under extreme circumstances (Njoku, 2017). African conflicts are often characterized by resource scarcity, weak governance, and ethnic tensions which exacerbate the vulnerabilities of women and children (Akinrinade & Ola, 2015). Cultural norms can also limit women's access to resources and decision-making processes making them more dependent on men and vulnerable to abuse. Despite these challenges, African women have demonstrated remarkable resilience engaging in grassroots peace initiatives and advocating for their rights.

Nigeria, popularly known as the giant of Africa and the most populated country in Africa has also witnessed numerous conflicts which consist of the Boko Haram insurgency in the northeast, the ongoing herder-farmer conflicts in the middlebelt, and the Niger Delta militancy. In these contexts, the roles and positions of women and children have been significantly affected (Noor et al., 2017; Njoku, 2017). These conflicts, driven by a combination of insurgencies, terrorist activities, and inter-communal violence, have deeply impacted the most vulnerable members of society women and children. The Boko Haram insurgency has had a profound impact on Nigerian women. Thousands of women have been abducted by the group, the most notable case being the kidnapping of 276 schoolgirls from Chibok in 2014. The abduction sparked international outrage and led to the #BringBackOurGirls campaign, which emphasized the role of women in advocating for the safe return of abducted children and the protection of girls' education (Okonjo-Iweala, 2016). The Nigerian government has been unable to fully address the issue of child recruitment by armed groups, particularly in the northeast. Boko Haram's abduction of young girls, often forcing them into marriage or using them as suicide bombers, has highlighted the vulnerability of children in conflict.

Understanding the concept of conflict and the drastic effect it has on both humans and the environment, this paper aims to investigate the position and role of women and children in conflict hotspots in Nigeria, with references to women's activities, politicians, and other professionals in the management and resolution of conflict.

Theoretical Foundations of the Study

This paper explains the position and functions of women and children in conflict hotspots, with Nigeria as its focus. To understand the depth of this issue, two theoretical frameworks are used: Feminist Theory and Human Security Theory. These theories offer valuable insights into the gendered dimensions of conflict and the broader implications for individual and community well-being.

Feminist Theory

The foundational belief behind feminist theory is that from the start of human civilization, women have been given a secondary status by masculine-dominated social discourse and Western philosophical tradition. The history of every civilization shows that women have always been undermined to a position where they have no means to re-claim their unique

identity unless and until they re-visit the history, explore it, and finally re-establish it through their own experiences and insights. To explore their own potential identities, women have to redefine themselves against the male-informed ideals and beliefs that are passed down from generation to generation. These beliefs have produced a suppressing system by creating female subjects who are conditioned to accept the values of the system (Javeed, 2020). Feminist theory has evolved through the contributions of various scholars and activists. Foundational works such as Simone de Beauvoir's *The Second Sex* (1949) and Betty Friedan's *The Feminine Mystique* (1963) laid the groundwork for this evolution. De Beauvoir challenged traditional notions of femininity and advocated for women's liberation, while Friedan addressed the dissatisfaction of women confined to domestic roles. Contemporary feminist scholars have expanded upon these works, analyzing the intersections of gender, race, class, and sexuality in various social contexts. The core tenets of feminist theory posit that gender roles and inequalities are socially constructed and perpetuated by patriarchal systems that marginalize women and other gender minorities. Feminist theory critiques traditional power structures and advocates for dismantling systemic oppression to achieve gender equality. In the context of conflict, feminist theorists argue that wars and conflicts are not gender-neutral; instead, they often exacerbate existing gender disparities and subject women and children to unique forms of violence and exploitation. (Becker, 2010).

Feminist theory provides a critical lens for examining conflict situations, particularly in contexts like Nigeria, where the impact is disproportionately felt by women and children. This perspective illuminates the unique challenges they encounter, including sexual violence, forced displacement, and exclusion from peacebuilding initiatives. Importantly, feminist theory recognizes women and children not merely as victims, but as active agents in conflict resolution and community rebuilding (Eagly, 2014). Furthermore, feminist perspectives have significantly reshaped traditional approaches to conflict resolution. Feminist scholars have critiqued realist paradigms in International Relations (IR), which often prioritize state-centric and militaristic solutions. (Lobb, 2013) Instead, feminist approaches advocate for solutions that consider the lived experiences of women and other marginalized groups, leading to more inclusive peace processes that address the root causes of conflict and promote sustainable peace.

Human Security Theory

The concept of Human Security was initiated by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in its 1994 Human Development Report. Economist Mahbub ul Haq and philosopher Amartya Sen were critical in shaping this paradigm, which widened the understanding of security beyond military considerations to include various dimensions affecting human well-being. The tenets of this theory lays importance on the security of individuals from critical and pervasive threats, including food, economic, environmental, health, personal, community, and political dimensions. It advocates for a public opinion approach to security, stating that threats to individual well-being can destabilize communities and nations (Richard, 2006). This theory underscores the interconnections of various security threats and the need for comprehensive strategies to address them.

The overall importance of Human Security Theory is to make sense of the implications that violence and instability have on the basic tenets of life, especially concerning women and children in the opportunity cost of conflict hotspots in Nigeria. It underscores the diverse types of security threats they confront, ranging from physical violence to economic deprivation and social marginalization. Such an approach is critical for designing treatments that tackle immediate safety issues and also offer long-term health and resiliency (Neville, 2007) Additionally, human security has been used as a lens through which to examine the effects of armed conflicts on vulnerable populations. Research, such as that by the Institute of

Justice and Reconciliation, discusses resource-based conflicts in Kenya's Isiolo County and their impact on human security, highlighting the importance of developing comprehensive approaches that target both short-term violence and long-term systemic issues. These approaches are closely associated with the fundamental principles of Human Security which address the well-being of people and communities.

Integrating Feminist and Human Security Theories

This is a more detailed perspective through the fusion of Feminist Theory and Human Security Theory that provides richness to the multi-faceted nature of conflict that women and children are forced to endure. Feminist Theory highlights how sociocultural factors manifest in a gendered dynamic in a conflict context, while Human Security Theory casts a wider net over the aspects of well-being affected by such an eventuality. Such an approach provides a more contextual comprehension of the specific needs and contributions of women and children in conflict environments, allowing for more effective and inclusive policies and interventions.

The more holistic approach through the merging of Feminist Theory and Human Security Theory, gives depth to the multiple-pronged aspects of conflict that women and children are made to face. Feminist Theory illustrates how socio-cultural factors play out in a gendered dynamic conflict environment, while Human Security Theory broadens the scope of human well-being compromised in such a scenario. Such of course is a much more contextual understanding of the needs and contributions of women and children in conflict environments, allowing for more.

Reactions and Effects of Conflict Hot Spot Experience on Gender-Based Violence and Exploitation during Conflicts on Women and Children in Nigeria

In the course of this study, the idea of conflict and its impact on women and children has been established. Nigeria has been plagued by numerous conflicts over the years, particularly in regions such as the North-East, North-West, and North-Central, where insurgencies, communal clashes, and banditry are dominant. The effect these conflicts have on women and children is majority of the time very critical. One key factor from these issues is gender-based violence and exploitation. These groups encountered different faces of conflict including, violence, rape, forced marriage, human trafficking, and child soldier recruitment, often with little protection or redress (Amnesty International, 2023; UNHCR, 2022).

The reactions to gender-based violence (GBV) in conflict zones vary among different stakeholders, including the government, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and international bodies. Despite a massive amount of intercessions, the existence of GBV in Nigerian conflict zones raises critical questions about the effectiveness of these responses and their impact on the victims. This study, therefore explores the reactions and effects of conflict hotspot experiences on GBV and the exploitation of women and children in Nigeria, using recent studies and reports as references. Pertinent to note is the fact that several regions in Nigeria have been severely affected by prolonged conflict, exacerbating the risks of GBV and exploitation among women and children.

The Boko Haram insurgency, which began in 2009, has caused immense suffering for women and children in Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa states. The group has abducted thousands of women and girls, subjecting them to sexual violence, forced marriages, and radicalization (International Crisis Group, 2023). Reports indicate that over 2.2 million people have been displaced due to Boko Haram's activities, with women and children making up a significant portion of the internally displaced persons (IDPs) (UNICEF, 2022). Also, the North-West region has witnessed increasing cases of banditry and mass

kidnappings, particularly in Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, and Sokoto states. Women and young girls are frequently kidnapped and forced into marriage or subjected to sexual exploitation by armed groups (Human Rights Watch, 2022). The North-Central region, particularly Benue, Plateau, and Nasarawa states, has been a hotspot for violent clashes between herders and farmers. These conflicts have led to mass displacements, and women and children in IDP camps remain vulnerable to sexual exploitation and abuse (Médecins, 2021).

However, the Nigerian government has attempted to address GBV through several policies and interventions: The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPP) 2015 criminalizes various forms of GBV, including rape, domestic violence, and harmful traditional practices (National Assembly of Nigeria, 2022). The Child Rights Act (CRA) 2003, aimed at protecting children from abuse, has not been fully implemented in all states, leaving many children vulnerable to exploitation (UNICEF, 2023). The Safe Schools Initiative (SSI) was introduced to protect children, especially girls, from school-related abductions, but its implementation has faced major challenges (Federal Ministry of Education, 2023). Despite these efforts, enforcement remains weak, and many survivors face stigma and legal barriers when seeking justice (Amnesty International, 2023).

UNHCR and UNICEF provide psychosocial support, legal aid, and emergency relief to survivors of sexual violence (UNHCR, 2022; UNICEF, 2022). Women Advocates Research and Documentation Centre (WARDC) works to empower women through legal assistance and policy advocacy (WARDC, 2023). The International Rescue Committee (IRC) runs safe spaces for women and girls in IDP camps and provides medical care to GBV survivors (IRC, 2022). In many communities, survivors of GBV face stigma and rejection, making it difficult for them to seek justice or reintegrate into society (International Peace Institute, 2022). Traditional and religious leaders sometimes intervene in GBV cases, but their solutions often emphasize reconciliation rather than justice for survivors.

Physical and Health Consequences of this show that women and girls who experience sexual violence often suffer from sexually transmitted infections (STIs), traumatic fistula, and other reproductive health complications (Médecins Sans Frontières, 2021). High maternal mortality rates have been recorded among survivors of sexual violence, particularly those forced into early marriages (World Health Organization, 2023). Many survivors of GBV in conflict zones suffer from Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety (UNHCR, 2022). Children exposed to conflict violence exhibit aggressive behaviors, withdrawal symptoms, and difficulty reintegrating into normal life (UNESCO, 2023). Many women and girls are forced to abandon their education due to pregnancies resulting from rape or because of displacement (UNESCO, 2023). The economic impact of displacement leaves women vulnerable to exploitation and forced labor, making it difficult to achieve self-sufficiency (World Bank, 2023). Also, the weak judicial system and lack of prosecution for perpetrators contribute to a culture of impunity (Human Rights Watch, 2022). Many survivors do not report their cases due to fear of stigma, retaliation, and lack of legal representation (Amnesty International, 2023).

The Socio-Economic Consequences of Conflict on Women and Children in both Urban and Rural Conflict Zones in Nigeria:

From this study, it can already be deduced that conflicts in Nigeria have had devastating socio-economic effects on vulnerable populations, particularly women and children. Both urban and rural conflict zones experience different yet severe consequences. In rural areas, insurgencies, banditry, and communal clashes disrupt agriculture, displace families, and expose women and children to extreme poverty and gender-based violence (UNHCR, 2023). In urban conflict zones, riots, ethno-religious tensions, and gang violence increase unemployment, limit access to education, and worsen economic disparities

(World Bank, 2023). Women and children, often considered secondary actors in conflict discourse, bear the brunt of socio-economic instability. This study also intends to examine the socio-economic consequences of conflict in Nigeria, differentiating between the urban and rural contexts and providing recent data and scholarly references.

This study has established that rural communities in conflict zones such as the North-East, North-West, and North-Central regions of Nigeria heavily rely on agriculture. However, conflicts have led to: Boko Haram insurgency, and farmer-herder clashes have devastated agricultural activities, reducing food production and leading to widespread hunger (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2023). Women, who constitute a significant percentage of the agricultural workforce, lose their means of income due to displacement and insecurity (World Food Programme, 2023). This economic devastation pushes many women into informal or exploitative labor, including transactional sex, in a bid to survive (Amnesty International, 2023). The position and role of women and children in conflict hotspots, such as Afghanistan under the influence of Islamic fundamentalist groups, highlight the severe socio-cultural restrictions imposed on these vulnerable populations, where women's activities are often curtailed, limiting their participation in politics, professional roles, and conflict resolution efforts (Ibe, Iroye, & Ibebunjo, 2022).

Also, the absence of security and law enforcement in rural conflict zones exposes women and children to severe gender-based violence (GBV) as Boko Haram and armed bandits have used sexual violence as a weapon of war, leading to increased cases of sexually transmitted infections and unwanted pregnancies (Human Rights Watch, 2022). Whereas, displacement and economic instability force many families to marry off their daughters at a young age to reduce household burdens (UNICEF, 2023). Human trafficking efforts disposition women and children exploiting their weaknesses or illiteracy in the name of offering them safety and employment (International Organization for Migration, 2023).

Children need to be educated but due to conflicts and exploitations, over 1.3 million children have been forced out of school due to the destruction of educational facilities in conflict-affected areas (UNESCO, 2023). The kidnapping of schoolgirls, as in the Chibok and Dapchi abductions, has created fear, discouraging parents from sending their daughters to school (International Crisis Group, 2023). The long-term effect of this educational disruption is a generation of women and children who lack the necessary skills to participate in economic development, deepening poverty cycles.

The destruction of healthcare services has immensely caused a lot of damage, especially in rural areas for women and children, many women give birth in unsafe conditions due to the destruction of health centers (World Health Organization, 2023). The conflicted areas suffer and struggle with a lack of food storage which leads to malnutrition and sometimes death cases because the afflicted groups are barely being taken care of but rather more, neglected. (World Food Programme, 2023). Women have very sensitive areas and when not properly taken care of, can lead to cases such as sexual violence survivors, They often do not receive medical assistance, increasing risks of complications such as fistulas (Médecins, 2023).

The socio-economic consequences of conflict on women and children in the Urban afflicted zones seemingly rural areas, urban conflict zones such as Lagos, Kaduna, and Jos experience violent protests, religious riots, and gang-related violence leading to, the destruction of businesses and jobs, the source of livelihood of many individuals. Many women, particularly those engaged in small-scale businesses, lose their sources of income due to market closures and destruction (World Bank, 2023). Ethno-religious violence left women and children stranded as their businesses and homes were burnt down (International Crisis Group, 2023). In such situations as these, women and children are left helpless and desperate making them result to begging and engaging in prostitution (Human Rights Watch, 2023). Urban conflict zones create conditions where children become increasingly vulnerable to criminal activities, In areas like Lagos and Kano, displaced or

orphaned children are often recruited into violent street gangs or radical movements, and through this, the lifestyle of the children suffer due to exposure to the wrong circumstance (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2023). Many children are forced into hawking, domestic servitude, or factory work under exploitative conditions (UNICEF, 2023). In conflict hotspots, women and children often bear the brunt of violence and instability, yet women have emerged as pivotal agents in conflict resolution and peacebuilding efforts, as evidenced by their roles in post-genocide Rwanda, where women's activism and leadership significantly contributed to rebuilding communities and fostering reconciliation (Ibe, Iroye, & Ibebunjo, 2023).

Urban conflict situations also contribute to rising cases of gender-based violence, economic hardships, and post-traumatic stress from conflict often leading to higher incidences of intimate partner violence (Amnesty International, 2023). Women displaced by urban conflicts often become victims of sex trafficking networks operating in major cities and in these cases, women are exploited because of a lack of knowledge of their rights and desperation (International Organization for Migration, 2023).

The stress and trauma of conflict create severe mental health challenges for women and children such as an increase in PTSD, depression, and anxiety, conflict survivors suffer from severe psychological distress, leading to a rise in suicide rates among dis-positioned women who are most times never fully recover from it making them feel dead and empty (World Health Organization, 2023). Limited access to mental health care, Nigeria's mental health infrastructure is poor and weak, and urban IDP camps lack sufficient psychosocial support services leaving the conflicted groups wandering around lifelessly (UNHCR, 2023). In conflict hotspots like the Gaza Strip, women and children often bear the brunt of violence and instability, yet women have emerged as pivotal actors in conflict resolution and peace building efforts, leveraging their roles as caregivers, politicians, and activists to advocate for sustainable solutions, as highlighted in studies exploring conflict resolution strategies in such regions (Ibe, Iroye, & Ibebunjo, 2023).

The Roles Played By Women in Peace-Building and Conflict Reconstruction with Nigeria as the Focus

Conflicts have been a reoccurring challenge in Nigeria, manifesting in various forms such as insurgency, communal clashes, religious violence, and much more. Women, often considered victims of conflict, have emerged as key agents of peacebuilding and reconstruction in post-conflict societies. Despite facing gender-based violence, displacement, and socio-economic hardships, women in Nigeria have played crucial roles in mediation, advocacy, and rebuilding efforts (UN Women, 2023). This creates insights into the roles women play in peacebuilding and conflict reconstruction in Nigeria, highlighting their contributions to mediation, governance, community development, and post-conflict rehabilitation.

Peacebuilding:

Peacebuilding refers to activities aimed at preventing the outbreak, escalation, and recurrence of conflict. It includes mediation, reconciliation, and institutional reform (International Crisis Group, 2023). Women in Nigeria engage in peacebuilding by leading dialogue processes, advocating for justice, and fostering social cohesion in conflict-affected communities. On the other hand, conflict reconstruction involves rebuilding communities and institutions after violence. Women play significant roles in economic recovery, reintegration of displaced persons, and rebuilding social infrastructures such as schools and healthcare systems (World Bank, 2023).

Women have been instrumental in negotiating peace in Nigeria's conflict zones through, mediation in communal and ethnic conflicts, women-led organizations, such as the Women's Peace Network, have facilitated peace dialogues between warring communities in Plateau, Kaduna, and Benue states. Despite how society has tried to limit the activities of women and rather domesticate them, women still rise and have been seen to be one of the major groups driving and advocating for peace

(International Crisis Group, 2023). Some Nigerian women leaders have participated in negotiations with insurgent groups, advocating for ceasefires and the release of abducted women and children (UNHCR, 2023). Christian and Muslim women have collaborated in interfaith peace initiatives to promote religious tolerance and end sectarian violence (UN Women, 2023).

Despite these efforts, women remain underrepresented in official peace negotiations due to cultural and institutional barriers. Women in political and governance positions play a vital role in creating policies that promote peace and social stability: Female politicians have championed laws such as the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPP) to address gender-based violence, a major driver of conflict (National Assembly of Nigeria, 2023). Women-led security committees have helped reduce local violence by engaging with youth at risk of radicalization, these groups are now being educated instead of being neglected (Human Rights Watch, 2023). Organizations such as the Women Advocates Research and Documentation Centre (WARDC) continue to push for greater female representation in governance (WARDC, 2023).

Women play key roles in rebuilding communities after conflict by focusing on economic development and social stability: In Borno and Adamawa, displaced women have formed economic cooperatives that provide financial support and job opportunities for victims of conflict (World Bank, 2023). Women-run organizations offer vocational training programs to reintegrate former child soldiers and displaced youth into society (UNESCO, 2023). Women-led organizations provide the necessary needs and facilities such as trauma counseling and healthcare services to survivors of war and sexual violence (Médecins, 2023).

Despite their significant contributions, Nigerian women face multiple challenges in peacebuilding efforts: Many communities uphold patriarchal norms that exclude women from leadership roles in conflict resolution (Amnesty International, 2023). Women's voices are often ignored in official peace processes, leading to male-dominated negotiations because of the ideology existing in society (International Crisis Group, 2023). Female peace activists are at high risk of violence, including targeted attacks by insurgent groups and threats from male-dominated political structures but in all these, these groups will not back down but continue to advocate for what is rightfully theirs. Women are known for their resilience and strength and as much as conditions try to bring them down, they remain huge contributors to peace-building in Nigeria (Human Rights Watch, 2023). Women's organizations receive limited funding for their peacebuilding initiatives, making it difficult to sustain long-term programs (World Bank, 2023).

The Nigerian government should implement policies that mandate at least 30% female representation in peace negotiation teams (National Assembly of Nigeria, 2023). Political parties should support women's leadership in governance and security sectors. The government should establish protection mechanisms for female peace activists, including legal protections against gender-based threats (Amnesty International, 2023). Community policing initiatives should integrate women into security structures. International donors and government agencies should increase financial support for women-led cooperatives and businesses in conflict-affected areas (World Bank, 2023). Skills development and entrepreneurship programs should be expanded to provide economic independence for women in post-conflict settings. Public awareness campaigns should be launched to challenge gender norms that exclude women from peace processes (UNESCO, 2023). Schools should incorporate peace education to encourage future female leadership in conflict resolution.

Conclusion

This study has critically examined the position and role of women and children in conflict hotspots, with a particular focus on Nigeria. The research underscores the disproportionate impact of conflict on women and children, revealing patterns of gender-based violence, forced displacement, economic hardships, and socio-political exclusion. While women and children

have often been perceived as passive victims of conflict, this study highlights their active roles in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Nigerian women, despite facing systemic barriers, have demonstrated resilience and leadership in post-conflict reconstruction, advocating for justice, reconciliation, and socio-economic recovery. The application of Feminist Theory and Human Security Theory provides a comprehensive understanding of the challenges women and children face in conflict zones. Feminist Theory highlights the systemic gender inequalities that exacerbate vulnerabilities during conflict, while Human Security Theory broadens the scope to include various aspects of well-being, such as economic stability, health security, and access to education. Together, these frameworks provide a holistic perspective that informs sustainable interventions for protecting and empowering women and children in conflict settings. This research contributes to academic discourse by emphasizing the need for gender-sensitive policies in conflict resolution and post-conflict recovery. The study also provides practical recommendations for policymakers, civil society organizations, and international agencies to enhance the protection, participation, and well-being of women and children in conflict-affected regions. Identity-based conflicts in African cultures, as explored by Ibe, Iroye, and Ibebunjo (2024), highlight the critical roles women and children play in conflict hotspots, often as both vulnerable groups and agents of change, with women particularly emerging as pivotal figures in peacebuilding, advocacy, and the management of conflict resolution efforts.

The following key findings therefore emerged from this paper:

- 1) **Gender-Based Violence and Exploitation:** Women and children in Nigeria's conflict zones are particularly vulnerable to sexual violence, forced marriages, human trafficking, and domestic abuse. Boko Haram and other insurgent organizations have repeatedly exploited sexual violence as a weapon of war, causing significant physical and psychological harm.
- 2) **Forced Displacement and Economic Hardship:** Conflict has resulted in mass displacement, with women and children making up the majority of internally displaced persons (IDPs). Economic opportunities for displaced women are limited, forcing many into exploitative labor, prostitution, or reliance on humanitarian aid.
- 3) **Educational Disruptions:** The study found that conflict has significantly disrupted education, with millions of children unable to attend school due to displacement, insecurity, or targeted attacks on schools. This educational gap affects future economic and social development.
- 4) **Healthcare and Psychological Trauma:** Women and children in conflict zones face inadequate healthcare services, especially concerning maternal health and psychological support. Survivors of sexual violence often lack access to medical care, and many suffer from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).
- 5) **Women as Agents of Peace and Conflict Resolution:** Despite these challenges, women have played active roles in conflict resolution and peacebuilding in Nigeria. Female-led organizations and grassroots movements have mediated peace agreements, facilitated community reconciliation, and advocated for victims' rights.
- 6) **Limited Representation in Peace Processes:** Women remain underrepresented in formal peace negotiations and political decision-making. Patriarchal norms, cultural restrictions, and institutional barriers limit their participation in shaping post-conflict policies.
- 7) **Inadequate Legal and Policy Interventions:** Although Nigeria has adopted legal frameworks such as the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPP) 2015 and the Child Rights Act (2003), enforcement remains weak. Many survivors of gender-based violence face stigma and limited access to justice.

- 8) **Impact of Urban and Rural Conflicts:** While rural conflict zones experience direct violence and displacement, urban areas suffer from increased crime, gender-based violence, and economic instability. Women and children in cities affected by gang violence and political unrest face exploitation and social marginalization.
- 9) **Community-Based Peacebuilding Efforts:** Many women-led initiatives at the grassroots level have been successful in promoting peace, education, and economic empowerment. However, these efforts often lack sufficient funding and institutional support.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthening Legal and Policy Frameworks

- The Nigerian government should enforce and expand the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPP) 2015 to ensure stronger protections against gender-based violence in conflict zones.
- The Child Rights Act (CRA) 2003 should be fully implemented in all Nigerian states to safeguard children from abuse and exploitation.
- Strengthen legal mechanisms to prosecute perpetrators of sexual violence in conflict zones and provide legal aid for survivors.

2. Enhancing Women's Participation in Peace Processes

- A minimum 30% quota for women's representation should be mandated in peace negotiations, conflict resolution panels, and political decision-making bodies.
- Women should be included in security sector reforms, allowing greater participation in law enforcement, military, and intelligence agencies.
- Political parties should support and promote female leadership in governance and policymaking.

3. Addressing Gender-Based Violence and Health Needs

- Establish more safe houses and rehabilitation centers for survivors of sexual violence in conflict-affected regions.
- Improve access to medical care for victims, including post-rape treatment, psychosocial support, and reproductive health services.
- Implement large-scale mental health programs to address PTSD, anxiety, and depression among women and children affected by conflict.

4. Economic Empowerment and Livelihood Support

- Develop women-led economic cooperatives in conflict-affected areas to provide financial independence and livelihood opportunities.
- Increase vocational training programs for displaced women and girls to enhance their employability and self-sufficiency.
- Provide microfinance support to enable women in conflict zones to start businesses and achieve economic resilience.

5. Ensuring Education for Conflict-Affected Children

- Strengthen the Safe Schools Initiative (SSI) to prevent attacks on educational institutions and improve security infrastructure in conflict-prone areas.
- Expand scholarship programs and alternative learning centers for displaced children and girls affected by conflict.

- Integrate peace education into school curricula to foster reconciliation and conflict prevention among youth.

6. Strengthening Security and Humanitarian Interventions

- Deploy community policing initiatives that integrate women into security and peacekeeping efforts.
- Increase funding for humanitarian organizations providing emergency aid, shelter, and medical assistance to displaced women and children.
- Improve the coordination between government agencies, NGOs, and international bodies to develop gender-sensitive humanitarian responses.

7. Promoting Community Engagement and Social Awareness

- Launch public awareness campaigns to challenge harmful gender norms that exclude women from leadership and decision-making roles.
- Train traditional and religious leaders to support women's involvement in peacebuilding and discourage practices that contribute to gender-based violence.
- Encourage media advocacy to highlight women's contributions to peace and security, promoting positive narratives of female leadership in conflict resolution.

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